

EARTH SCIENCES

TO THE PROBLEM OF CREATING A RESEARCH ALGORITHM IN THE SPHERE OF LAND USE IN CHERKASY REGION

Sopova N.

*student of the third (scientific) level of higher education,
specialty 103 "Earth Sciences",
Uman National University of Horticulture
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0597-5598>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15317854>*

Abstract

The article deals with the problem of creating an algorithm for research in the field of land use in Cherkasy region. The focus is on analyzing existing methods and approaches to assessing the efficiency of land use in the region. The authors propose a structured algorithm that includes the stages of collecting, processing and analyzing data on the state of land, as well as developing recommendations for optimizing land use. Particular attention is paid to taking into account environmental, social and economic factors. The proposed algorithm can be used as a tool for making managerial decisions and ensuring sustainable development of a particular region.

Keywords: land use, research algorithm, Cherkasy region, sustainable development, land resources.

Land use problems, as well as general environmental issues, are becoming increasingly acute due to the progressive depletion of land resources across the planet. The intensive development of degradation processes, such as erosion, salinization, desertification and soil pollution, causes not only a physical reduction in available land resources, but also a noticeable decrease in soil fertility. As a result, this deepens the global food crisis, jeopardizing the food security of millions of people.

Solving these multifaceted problems is the focus of attention of specialists from various fields, including natural and socio-economic sciences. State bodies, political figures, and international organizations are actively involved in this process. However, it is the geographical approach to studying land use issues that is extremely promising. It is based on a comprehensive analysis of the interaction of natural and anthropogenic factors that affect the structure, condition, and efficiency of land resource use in economic activities. Geographical research allows us to consider these problems systematically, assessing not only local consequences but also global trends, which makes it possible to develop effective strategies for sustainable land use [1; 5].

Natural processes that may be considered unfavorable from a human perspective – such as soil erosion, deflation, flooding, salinization, karst phenomena, etc. – play an integral role in the functioning of complex natural and economic systems. However, under conditions of intensification of economic activity, they acquire a destructive character, turning into factors of degradation. This phenomenon is caused not only by the direct impact of human activity, but also by the effect of synergistic action, when the mutual reinforcement of these processes contributes to their spread and intensification.

The intensification of degradation phenomena is often a consequence of imperfect land use, underestimation of the impact of natural conditions, or neglect

of ecological principles in economic activities [5]. For example, improper agricultural techniques, excessive irrigation, deforestation, or development of territories without taking into account their natural features can significantly accelerate such processes. The result is a loss of ecological balance, a decrease in land productivity, a decrease in biodiversity, and a deepening of environmental problems.

Understanding the complex interactions of these processes in natural and economic systems is an important task for scientists, planners, and managers. This requires a systemic approach, taking into account local characteristics and global trends, as well as developing strategies for adapting to changes and minimizing damage caused by both natural and anthropogenic factors.

Problems arising from human activities are becoming increasingly threatening. Solving these problems, in particular for the Cherkasy region, can be carried out through the following mechanisms:

- ✓ creation of an information database on the structure of the land fund;
- ✓ assessment of land condition;
- ✓ identification of land degradation factors and the degree of their impact in various physical and geographical conditions;
- ✓ assessing the consequences of various types of degradation processes;
- ✓ development of land quality standards by type of use (purpose);
- ✓ systemic analysis and integrated assessment of factors and environmental consequences of the manifestation of negative natural processes;
- ✓ zoning of the territory according to the degree of influence of factors of natural and anthropogenic pressure on the land and its consequences;
- ✓ development of solutions to limit land use and establish permissible norms of land load and development of systems of measures for land reclamation and search for optimal ways of rational land use.

To successfully complete the tasks, it is necessary to ensure a systematic approach to studying the outlined problem. This approach is implemented using an algorithm (Fig. 1), which not only coordinates and regulates

the research process, but also guarantees the objectivity, reliability and scientific validity of the results obtained. This ensures consistency of actions at all stages of the research and the achievement of the most accurate conclusions.

Fig. 1. Algorithm for research into land use problems in Cherkasy region (author's own development)

An algorithm can be considered as a kind of program of actions, a structured scheme or model that determines the activities of a scientist. It sets the logic, sequence and clear phasing of all actions aimed at achieving the research goal. An extended version of the algorithm not only provides the organization of the process, but also allows you to specify the spatio-temporal parameters of the research object. This includes determining the sample size for statistical analysis, which is important for obtaining representative results. Each stage of the algorithm is closely related to the previous and subsequent ones, forming a coherent logical structure that contributes to the systematicity, coherence and efficiency of scientific research [3].

The first stage of this study involves thorough preparatory work, which involves the collection, systematization, and analysis of a large amount of information. At this stage, an important role is played by the creation of analytical and synthetic maps, which should become the basis for further generalization of the obtained data. These maps provide visualization and systematization of key characteristics of the studied processes and phenomena, which allows for their comprehensive assessment [2]. Based on this assessment, practical recommendations are developed aimed at eliminating, reducing or neutralizing the negative impact of degradation processes in the field of land use, ensuring sustainable development of territories.

The choice of research methods has a direct and interdependent relationship with the defined goal. The goal of the research sets the direction, choosing methods for collecting primary information, processing it and analyzing the results obtained [1]. At the same time, the methods used actively influence the goal itself, contributing to its clarification, detailing and deepening. Thus, methods and purpose are in dynamic interaction: the purpose forms the requirements for research tools, and the tools, in turn, help to more clearly define, adapt, and improve the research goal, ensuring its compliance with the realities of the research process.

The purpose and methods of the study directly define the tasks, which are key stages in the process of conducting the study from beginning to end. The tasks break down the overall goal into specific, achievable steps, each of which requires the use of certain methods and approaches for collecting, processing, and analyzing information [1]. This allows you to clearly structure the research, guarantee a logical sequence of actions and ensure the effective achievement of the set goals. In turn, each task contributes to a detailed study of individual aspects of the object or phenomenon under study, helping to gradually approach general conclusions and recommendations.

In any scientific research, regardless of its nature, the laws of dialectics are directly or indirectly present. In the process of developing an algorithm, one of the main dialectical laws is clearly manifested - the law of unity and struggle of opposites. This contrast is manifested between the complexity and multifacetedness of objective reality (in our case, a stable and complex land use system) and the ideal or optimal land use model, which must correspond to the specific conditions of a particular region, in particular physical, geographical and socio-economic characteristics. This contradiction between the existing reality and the theoretical model creates conditions for finding ways to improve the land use system, develop practical recommendations, and,

ultimately, achieve optimal results in natural resource management [4].

The systems approach helps to overcome this contradiction to a large extent, allowing to simplify real, complex objects to a more generalized model, which will be representative of a wide range of objects, processes and phenomena. Such a model can be applied not only to a specific situation, but also to a large number of diverse objects, covering different territories and time periods. Thanks to a systems approach, it is possible to create a holistic, structured picture of reality, which allows you to effectively take into account all important factors and connections, and also provides the opportunity to predict the development of events in the future. This allows you to make informed decisions that meet specific requirements and conditions, taking into account both current and future needs.

The proposed research algorithm is tested on the example of Cherkasy region, which is typical and representative for other administrative regions of Ukraine, but at the same time it has universality and can be applied to any territory. This approach allows adapting the algorithm to the specific conditions of other regions, taking into account the peculiarities of local natural, economic and social factors. The algorithm provides flexibility in use, allowing for effective research and assessment of land use processes and their changes in different territories, thus ensuring the possibility of its widespread application in other regions of the country.

References:

1. Sopov D. S., Sopova N. V. Constructive-geographical and environmental research of land resources: methodological principles. *Екологічні науки: науково-практичний журнал*. 2023. № 1(46). С. 150–152. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32846/2306-9716/2023.eco.1-46.25>
2. N. Sopova, O. Kyseliova, Yu. Kyselov, I. Cherednychenko and D. Sopov. Mapping the erosion damage of agricultural landscapes in Cherkasy region. *International Conference of Young Professionals «GeoTerrace-2024»*, 7–9 October 2024, Lviv, Ukraine. P. 1–5. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3997/2214-4609.2024510082>
3. Sopova N. V. Conceptual and terminological apparatus of land use at the local level. *Природнична освіта та наука*. 2024. Випуск 1. С. 68–78. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32782/NSER/2024-1.10>
4. Dmytro Sopov, Mehriban Shchebets. To the problem of methods in land management and cadastral research: geographical approach. *Innovative projects and paradigms of international education. A collection of theses: materials of I International multidisciplinary scientific and practical Internet conference «Innovative projects and paradigms of international education» (Georgia, Tbilisi, Ukraine, Kyiv, February 28 – March 1, 2023)*, Georgian Aviation University, 2023, P. 186–188.
5. Sopov D., Sopova N. Degraded and disturbed land: towards a definition of the concepts. *Теорія і практика розвитку агропромислового комплексу та сільських територій : матеріали XXIV Міжнародного науково-практичного форуму, 4–6 жовтня 2023 р. Львів: ЛНУП, 2023. С. 380–382. URL: <https://repository.lnau.edu.ua/xmlui/handle/123456789/901>*